

Supplementary Information

Checking for Potential for phenotype heterogeneity in BioVU Samples

POAG was ascertained in the BioVU dataset using phecodes in VUMC electronic health records. All subjects (n=144,017) with an ophthalmology examination code (CPT = 92002, 92004, 92012, or 92014) were selected using at least two instances of POAG phecode that covers ICD-9 and/or ICD-10 codes 365.11, H40.11XX, 365.12, H40.12XX (n=17,824) while controls exclude those with codes for glaucoma or optic nerve disease (365.XX, 377.XX, H40.XXXX, H47.XXXX (n=53,919). The groups were then filtered to include only subjects with genotyping data from Illumina MEGA-Array.

The de-identified electronic health records of the glaucoma subjects were then reviewed by their BioVU number to confirm the diagnoses. The patients' names, addresses, other forms of identification, and the treating physicians' names were removed. Records which were available included the problem list stating POAG or NTG, medication lists, clinical notes including detailed ophthalmic examinations, ophthalmic operative notes, correspondence letters and discharge summaries. Additional high-level confirmation included an anterior segment examination without secondary-glaucoma evidence, and open angles by gonioscopy.

Only those subjects (n=1040) who had POAG reported in any of the above categories by the treating physicians were included as cases in the manual review. Any subject, who was coded for POAG without supporting confirmation or who had contradictory information in the medical record, was excluded to minimize inclusion errors. Supporting information including: reported peripheral vision loss, intraocular pressure, glaucomatous optic nerve appearance, glaucoma surgeries and use of glaucoma medications was reviewed and noted. A total of 716 individuals who had MEGA array genotyped have their EHR manually curated. A total of 220 out of the 716 individuals conflicted with manually curated records of which 172 are those with only a single ICD9+ICD10 mention of POAG. A total of 48 phecode assignments conflicted with manually curated records: 5 cases were missed by phecode phenotyping, 4 were pigmentary glaucoma, 7 POAG suspect, 9 pseudoexfoliation syndromes (XFS) and 23 primary angle closure glaucoma (PACG) (Suppl. Table

S2). Using any mention of ICD9 or ICD10 POAG had a far much higher number of conflicts (114) with manually curated information. Thus conservatively, we estimate that ~1.2% (~320) and ~3.2% (~560) might potentially be XFS and PACG cases, respectively, among the total GBMI 26,848 POAG cases.

Therefore, as further quality check step, we compared our GBMI-IGGC-GGLAD meta-analysis signals with well powered GWASs for XFS and PACG, and determined that three of the loci might be attributed to these two glaucoma subtypes: 1) The rs3825942_*LOXLI* loci that is main XFS signal and previously reported in GWAS of glaucoma or recent POAG study that include Biobank level.^{1,2} 2) The rs11024102_*PLEKHA7* has been associated only with PACG and glaucoma in East Asian ancestry individuals, while the lead variant in rs58812088_*FNDC3B* in our study is just ~12kb away from and in high LD ($r^2=0.7$) with PACG lead variant in rs16856870_*FNDC3B* locus.^{3,4} However, three loci: rs993471_*COL11A1*, rs2276035_*ARHGEF12*, rs12150284_*GAS7* have previously been shown to be POAG-PACG shared loci.^{4,5}

Groningen Longitudinal Glaucoma Study (GLGS)

The GLGS study consists of cases from the Groningen Longitudinal Glaucoma Study (GLGS). The GLGS consisted of Dutch individuals with a diagnosis of POAG from the hospital-based Groningen Longitudinal Glaucoma Study (GLGS). The original GLGS cohort has been described in detail by Heeg et al. (2005).⁶ After the inclusion of the initial cohort in 2000-2001, the GLGS continued as a dynamic population, that is, new participants were added during follow-up. We included glaucoma patients who visited the outpatient department of the University Medical Center Groningen in 2015 and who gave written informed consent for a blood sample being taken for genetic analyses. In the GLGS, glaucoma patients had to show glaucomatous visual field loss in at least one eye. For glaucomatous visual field loss, two consecutive tests had to be abnormal in at least one eye, after an initial test that was discarded to reduce the influence of learning. Defects had to be compatible with glaucoma and without any other explanation. Those with pseudoexfoliative or pigment dispersion glaucoma or a history of angle-closure or secondary glaucoma were excluded, leaving only POAG patients.⁷ In GLGS, genomic DNA was extracted from the peripheral blood, using Gentra Systems Purogene chemistry. The genotyping was done

using the Illumina Infinium Global Screening Array® (GSA) MultiEthnic Disease beadchip version, which contains 692,367 markers.^{8,9}

Biobanks that contributed GWAS summary statistics to POAG study

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BioMe - The Mount Sinai BioMe Biobank

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(1) Department of Genetics, University of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, The Netherlands

(2) Department of Pediatrics, University of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, The Netherlands

(3) Department of Epidemiology, University of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, The Netherlands

(4) Institute for Molecular Bioscience, The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia.

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UK Biobank

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REFERENCES

1. Aung, T. et al. Genetic association study of exfoliation syndrome identifies a protective rare variant at LOXL1 and five new susceptibility loci. *Nat. Genet.* 49, 993–1004 (2017).
2. Buniello, A. et al. The NHGRI-EBI GWAS Catalog of published genome-wide association studies, targeted arrays and summary statistics 2019. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 47, D1005–D1012 (2019).
3. Vithana, E. N. et al. Genome-wide association analyses identify three new susceptibility loci for primary angle closure glaucoma. *Nat. Genet.* 44, 1142–1146 (2012).
4. Khor, C. C. et al. Genome-wide association study identifies five new susceptibility loci for primary angle closure glaucoma. *Nat. Genet.* 48, 556–562 (2016).
5. Choquet, H. et al. A multiethnic genome-wide association study of primary open-angle glaucoma identifies novel risk loci. *Nat. Commun.* 9, 2278 (2018).
6. Heeg, G. P., Blanksma, L. J., Hardus, P. L. L. & Jansonius, N. M. The Groningen Longitudinal Glaucoma Study. I. Baseline sensitivity and specificity of the frequency doubling perimeter and the GDx nerve fibre analyser. *Acta Ophthalmologica Scandinavica* vol. 83 46–52 (2005).
7. Bonnemaier, P. W. M. et al. Differences in clinical presentation of primary open-angle glaucoma between African and European populations. *Acta Ophthalmol.* 99, e1118–e1126 (2021).
8. Lo Faro, V., Ten Brink, J. B., Snieder, H., Jansonius, N. M. & Bergen, A. A. Genome-wide CNV investigation suggests a role for cadherin, Wnt, and p53 pathways in primary open-angle glaucoma. *BMC Genomics* 22, 590 (2021).
9. Lo Faro, V. et al. Mitochondrial genome study identifies association between primary open-angle glaucoma and variants in MT-CYB, MT-ND4 genes and haplogroups. *Front. Genet.* 0, (1AD).
10. Tsoi, H. et al. A novel missense mutation in CCDC88C activates the JNK pathway and causes a dominant form of spinocerebellar ataxia. *J. Med. Genet.* 51, 590–595 (2014).
11. Wang, H.-Y. et al. Protein Kinase A-Mediated Septin7 Phosphorylation Disrupts Septin Filaments and Ciliogenesis. *Cells* 10, (2021).
12. Scheffer, D. I., Shen, J., Corey, D. P. & Chen, Z.-Y. Gene Expression by Mouse Inner Ear Hair Cells during Development. *Journal of Neuroscience* vol. 35 6366–6380 (2015).
13. Wu, M.-M. et al. Lovastatin attenuates hypertension induced by renal tubule-specific knockout of ATP-binding cassette transporter A1, by inhibiting epithelial sodium channels. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* 176, 3695–3711 (2019).

14. Zappaterra, M., Gioiosa, S., Chillemi, G., Zambonelli, P. & Davoli, R. Muscle transcriptome analysis identifies genes involved in ciliogenesis and the molecular cascade associated with intramuscular fat content in Large White heavy pigs. *PLoS One* 15, e0233372 (2020).
15. Wheway, G. et al. An siRNA-based functional genomics screen for the identification of regulators of ciliogenesis and ciliopathy genes. *Nat. Cell Biol.* 17, 1074–1087 (2015).
16. Klena, N. T., Gibbs, B. C. & Lo, C. W. Cilia and Ciliopathies in Congenital Heart Disease. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Biology* vol. 9 a028266 (2017).
17. Li, Y. et al. Global genetic analysis in mice unveils central role for cilia in congenital heart disease. *Nature* 521, 520–524 (2015).
18. Chevalier, B. et al. miR-34/449 control apical actin network formation during multiciliogenesis through small GTPase pathways. *Nat. Commun.* 6, 8386 (2015).
19. Shida, T., Cueva, J. G., Xu, Z., Goodman, M. B. & Nachury, M. V. The major alpha-tubulin K40 acetyltransferase alphaTAT1 promotes rapid ciliogenesis and efficient mechanosensation. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 107, 21517–21522 (2010).
20. Balestra, F. R., Strnad, P., Flückiger, I. & Gönczy, P. Discovering regulators of centriole biogenesis through siRNA-based functional genomics in human cells. *Dev. Cell* 25, 555–571 (2013).
21. He, X. et al. BAG6 is a novel microtubule-binding protein that regulates ciliogenesis by modulating the cell cycle and interacting with γ -tubulin. *Exp. Cell Res.* 387, 111776 (2020).
22. Rothé, B., Gagnieux, C., Leal-Esteban, L. C. & Constam, D. B. Role of the RNA-binding protein Bicaudal-C1 and interacting factors in cystic kidney diseases. *Cellular Signalling* vol. 68 109499 (2020).
23. Kwon, O. S. et al. Exon junction complex dependent mRNA localization is linked to centrosome organization during ciliogenesis. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 1351 (2021).
24. Jin, X. et al. L-type calcium channel modulates cystic kidney phenotype. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 1842, 1518–1526 (2014).
25. Rangel, L. et al. Caveolin-1 α regulates primary cilium length by controlling RhoA GTPase activity. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 1116 (2019).
26. Fu, S. et al. Primary Cilia as a Biomarker in Mesenchymal Stem Cells Senescence: Influencing Osteoblastic Differentiation Potency Associated with Hedgehog Signaling Regulation. *Stem Cells Int.* 2021, 8850114 (2021).
27. Doornbos, C. & Roepman, R. Moonlighting of mitotic regulators in cilium disassembly. *Cell. Mol. Life Sci.* 78, 4955–4972 (2021).

28. Sieving, P. A. et al. Ciliary neurotrophic factor (CNTF) for human retinal degeneration: phase I trial of CNTF delivered by encapsulated cell intraocular implants. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 103, 3896–3901 (2006).
29. Fischer, A. J. et al. Differential Gene Expression in Human Conducting Airway Surface Epithelia and Submucosal Glands. *American Journal of Respiratory Cell and Molecular Biology* vol. 40 189–199 (2009).
30. Failler, M. et al. Whole-genome screen identifies diverse pathways that negatively regulate ciliogenesis. *Mol. Biol. Cell* 32, 169–185 (2021).
31. Cao, J. et al. miR-129-3p controls cilia assembly by regulating CP110 and actin dynamics. *Nat. Cell Biol.* 14, 697–706 (2012).
32. Loktev, A. V. & Jackson, P. K. Neuropeptide Y family receptors traffic via the Bardet-Biedl syndrome pathway to signal in neuronal primary cilia. *Cell Rep.* 5, 1316–1329 (2013).
33. Marley, A., Choy, R. W.-Y. & von Zastrow, M. GPR88 reveals a discrete function of primary cilia as selective insulators of GPCR cross-talk. *PLoS One* 8, e70857 (2013).
34. Angrisani, A., Di Fiore, A., De Smaele, E. & Moretti, M. The emerging role of the KCTD proteins in cancer. *Cell Commun. Signal.* 19, 56 (2021).
35. Shamseldin, H. E. et al. The morbid genome of ciliopathies: an update. *Genet. Med.* 22, 1051–1060 (2020).
36. Das, A., Qian, J. & Tsang, W. Y. USP9X counteracts differential ubiquitination of NPHP5 by MARCH7 and BBS11 to regulate ciliogenesis. *PLoS Genet.* 13, e1006791 (2017).
37. McDonough, J. E. et al. Gene correlation network analysis to identify regulatory factors in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis. *Thorax* 74, 132–140 (2019).
38. Bachmann-Gagescu, R. et al. The Ciliopathy Protein CC2D2A Associates with NINL and Functions in RAB8-MICAL3-Regulated Vesicle Trafficking. *PLoS Genet.* 11, e1005575 (2015).
39. Zhou, J., Yang, F., Leu, N. A. & Wang, P. J. MNS1 is essential for spermiogenesis and motile ciliary functions in mice. *PLoS Genet.* 8, e1002516 (2012).
40. Avolio, R. et al. Protein Syndesmos is a novel RNA-binding protein that regulates primary cilia formation. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 46, 12067–12086 (2018).
41. Miyamoto, T. et al. Insufficiency of ciliary cholesterol in hereditary Zellweger syndrome. *EMBO J.* 39, e103499 (2020).
42. Chen, Q. et al. Prdx1 promotes the loss of primary cilia in esophageal squamous cell carcinoma. *BMC Cancer* 20, 372 (2020).

43. Vogt, J. et al. Mutation analysis of CHRNA1, CHRNB1, CHRND, and RAPSN genes in multiple pterygium syndrome/fetal akinesia patients. *Am. J. Hum. Genet.* 82, 222–227 (2008).
44. Martinez-Sanz, J. et al. Binding of human centrin 2 to the centrosomal protein hSfi1. *FEBS J.* 273, 4504–4515 (2006).
45. Minin, G. D. et al. Tmed2regulates Smoothed trafficking and Hedgehog signalling. doi:10.1101/2020.04.20.049957.
46. Jobling, A. I. et al. The Role of the Microglial Cx3cr1 Pathway in the Postnatal Maturation of Retinal Photoreceptors. *J. Neurosci.* 38, 4708–4723 (2018).
47. Westlake, C. J. et al. Primary cilia membrane assembly is initiated by Rab11 and transport protein particle II (TRAPP II) complex-dependent trafficking of Rabin8 to the centrosome. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 108, 2759–2764 (2011).
48. Karunakaran, K. B., Chaparala, S., Lo, C. W. & Ganapathiraju, M. K. Cilia interactome with predicted protein–protein interactions reveals connections to Alzheimer’s disease, aging and other neuropsychiatric processes. *Scientific Reports* vol. 10 (2020).
49. Kyun, M.-L. et al. Wnt3a Stimulation Promotes Primary Ciliogenesis through β -Catenin Phosphorylation-Induced Reorganization of Centriolar Satellites. *Cell Rep.* 30, 1447–1462.e5 (2020). 50. Thesis title "KRAB zinc finger protein-mediated control of transposon-embedded regulatory sequences from human germline to early embryos" (<https://infoscience.epfl.ch/record/286266>)
50. Thesis title "KRAB zinc finger protein-mediated control of transposon-embedded regulatory sequences from human germline to early embryos" (<https://infoscience.epfl.ch/record/286266>).